

Supplementary Materials: Analyzing Policy Mixes for the Circular Economy Transition: The Case of Recycled Plastics in Electronics

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A. Coding & interview guideline

This appendix section contains the coding and interview guidelines (tables A.1 and A.2) developed in this study. Three researchers initially set up, tested, and refined the coding guideline using two training documents. The two researchers then independently coded the ten legal policy documents, comparing the results and discussing the conflicts after coding of 2-3 legal texts. The four strategy documents were coded for the overall objectives and quantitative targets they include. The interview and coding guideline were set up using definitions of policy mix characteristics and operationalization frameworks from the literature (see, e.g. Reichardt and Rogge, 2016). In addition, when appropriate, the value chain actors were asked about their current processes used to recycle plastics or integrate recycled content into products.

Table A.1: Interview guide

Block	Category	Example questions
Technology & Process	Types of products	What types of plastics do you currently recycle from WEEE?
	Process requirements	What are the sorting requirements for recycling polymer type BB for product output AA?
	Technologies applied	Which sorting technologies do you use to achieve the desired purity levels?
Policy & Regulatory	Policy mix overview	What are the most relevant policies at the EU level that affect your business?
	Instrument mix verification	We have started gathering the most relevant measures at the EU-level, which measures did we forget to include?
	Policy mix characteristics	Do you see any gaps in the current policy landscape? Are policies concrete enough? Do actors know what they have to do? Are measures enough to clearly distribute responsibilities? Do you see any trade-offs or conflicts between different policies or policy goals? If so, where and why?
	General evaluation & Outlook	How well does the current policy mix work? How do you think the mix will develop in the near future? What are the instruments that should be introduced according to you?

Notes: This table illustrates the interview guide for the 20 semi-structured interviews. The guideline consists of two main blocks: technology & process-related questions and policy & regulatory questions. Questions belonging to the former were asked only to actors of the EEE value chain. Their exact nature varied depending on the actors' position in the value chain. The exemplary questions in this table were addressed at WEEE recyclers.

Table A.2: Legal text coding guideline

Dimension	Label	Definition	Chunk of Text	Example
Scope of legislation	Sector scope	Industrial sector that policy is restricted to	Word(s)	<i>EEE</i>
	Product or substance scope	Product(s) or substance(s) that policy is restricted to	Word(s)	<i>Medical devices; POPs</i>
Policy mix elements	Policy objective	General aims of policy	Sentence(s)	<i>The objectives of this Directive are to reduce the impact of certain plastic products on the environment [...].</i>
	Policy targets	Policy targets (quantitative) and their timeline	Sentence(s)	<i>From 2019, the minimum collection rate to be achieved shall be 65% [...].</i>
	Policy instruments	Instrument included in policy with or without direct actor reference	Sentence(s)	<i>Member states shall prohibit the disposal of separately collected WEEE which has not yet undergone the treatment specified in article 8.</i>
	Derogation, Exception, Explanation of instrument	Any passage that further explains the instrument, mentions conditions for exceptions or lays out general derogations of an instrument	Sentence(s) + Link to instrument quotation	<i>Member states may exempt from the requirement laid down in Article 23(1) establishments or undertakings for the following operations:[...].</i>
Target actor	Actor definition	Definition of value chain actor	Sentence(s)	<i>waste holder means the waste producer or the natural or legal person who is in possession of the waste;</i>
	Action definition	Definition of any step/procedure/process that is part of the plastics recycling or EEE value chain	Sentence(s)	<i>collection means the gathering of waste, including the preliminary sorting and preliminary storage of waste for the purposes of transport to a waste treatment facility.</i>
	Plastics or EEE value chain actor reference	Explicit mentioning of value chain actors addressed by policy instrument	Word(s) + Link to instrument quotation	<i>Waste treatment operator</i>

Notes: This table illustrates the guideline for coding the EU policy documents. The main outcome of coding the policy documents is an inventory of 97 policy instruments. The guideline is made up of 3 main dimensions, that each contain several codes. Since this paper focuses on the early-stage evaluation of the policy mix for circular plastics, the coding guideline focuses on eliciting the instrument mix for the different policies. The coding guideline does, therefore, not include any statements on policy processes between public actors at different government levels - i.e., how threshold levels are set or how policies are enforced and monitored.

B. Data sources

This appendix section gives a detailed list of data sources used in this study. The section includes tables on the legal document sources (table B.1), workshops and webinar sources (table B.2), and interview partners (table B.3).

Table B.1: List of legislation documents

Legislation	Publication Date	Last amended	Retrieved on	Source
Landfill Directive (1999/31/EC)	16.07.1999	14.06.2018	15.12.2023	eurlex
REACH Regulation (EC No 1907/2006)	18.12.2006	25.09.2023	14.12.2023	eurlex
Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC)	19.11.2008	30.05.2018	17.01.2024	eurlex
CLP Regulation (EC No 1272/2008)	16.12.2008	25.04.2023	14.01.2024	eurlex
RoHS Directive (2011/65/EU)	08.06.2011	28.10.2022	17.01.2024	eurlex
WEEE Directive (2012/19/EU)	04.07.2012	30.05.2018	17.01.2024	eurlex
Low Voltage Directive (2014/EU/35)	26.02.2014	-	15.12.2023	eurlex
POP Regulation (EU) 2019/1021	20.06.2019	30.05.2023	13.12.2023	eurlex
Waste Shipment Regulation (Proposal COM(2021) 709)	17.11.2022	-	16.01.2024	eurlex
Ecodesign Regulation (Proposal COM(2022) 142)	30.03.2022	-	15.01.2024	eurlex
New Circular Economy Action Plan (COM (2020) 98)	11.03.2020	-	15.07.2023	eurlex
Plastics Strategy (COM (2018) 28)	16.01.2018	-	14.07.2023	eurlex
Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (COM (2020) 667)	14.10.2020	-	20.09.2023	eurlex
New Industrial Strategy (COM (2020) 102)	10.03.2020	-	30.09.2023	eurlex

Notes: This table shows the list of legal documents that were qualitatively coded for this analysis. Note that the amendment date is based on the date the legal documents were retrieved for this study.

Table B.2: List of workshops, webinars, and conferences

Date	Title	Institution/Host	Type
22.09.2022	<i>Political and regulatory framework for circular consumer electronics</i>	CiCEL - Circularity e.V.	Webinar
13.10.2022	<i>E-Waste: Are recycled content quotas the right way?</i>	CiCEL - Circularity e.V.	Webinar
11.05.2023	<i>Plastics recycling: economic and regulatory barriers</i>	CiCEL - Circularity e.V.	Webinar
02.06.2023	<i>Annual CiCEL conference</i>	CiCEL - Circularity e.V.	Conference
13.09.2023	<i>Stakeholder workshop on legislative landscape</i>	INCREASE Project	Workshop

Notes: This table summarizes the webinar and workshops data sources that were used for this study. The conference and the workshop were taking place on-site.

Table B.3: List of interviewees

Role	Actor Group	Date	#	Duration	Country
Technical Regulatory Affairs Specialist/expert for circular plastics	EEE Brand Owner	05.10.2023	1	01.27 h	Central Europe
	Research Institute	16.10.2023	1	01.03 h	Northern Europe
Manager Business Development	Plastics Recycler	19.10.2023	2	02.30 h	Western Europe
		18.12.2023			
General Director	PRO	25.10.2023	1	01.00 h	EU-wide
CEO	Environmental Consulting	30.10.2023	1	00.54 h	Central Europe
Senior Recycling Coordinator	PRO	09.11.2023	1	00.50 h	Western Europe
Director Environmental Policy	Trade Association	15.11.2023	1	01.06 h	EU-wide
Partner	Environmental Consulting	29.11.2023	1	00.43 h	Central Europe
Head of department chemical safety (retired)	National policymaker	01.12.2023	1	01.03 h	Central Europe
Head of R&D	Plastics Recycler	04.12.2023	1	01.00 h	Western Europe
Research Associate	Research Institute	07.12.2023	1	01.01 h	Central Europe
General Managing Director	Plastic Converter	13.12.2023	1	01.11 h	EU-wide
CEO	WEEE Recycler	15.12.2023	1	00.50 h	Central Europe
Commercial Director	WEEE Processor	19.12.2023	1	01.14 h	Western Europe
General Manager (retired)	Plastics Recycler	20.12.2023	1	01.39 h	Central Europe
Policy Advisor	EU Policymaker	20.12.2023	1	00.58 h	EU-wide
Policy officer	EU Policymaker	05.01.2024	1	00.41 h	EU-wide
Programme Managers	NGO	08.01.2024	1	01.00 h	EU-wide
Policy officer	EU Policymaker	23.01.2024	1	00.52 h	EU-wide
<i>Total: 20 interviews of 21.12h</i>					

Notes: This table gives an overview of all interviews conducted during this study. All interviews were carried out online.

C. Results tables

This appendix section includes additional tables on the results of the policy mix analysis. Tables C.1 and C.2 provide additional information on the types and purposes of the instruments, as well as the value chain actors that they explicitly refer to. Table C.3 highlights the qualitative evaluation of policy instruments. Table C.4 gives the complete list of 97 policy instruments that were coded from 10 legal documents. Table C.5 shows how the actors were grouped according to the definition given in the legal documents. Finally, figure 1 illustrates a stylized value chain for plastic recycling in EEE.

Table C.1: Instruments with actor specification and type

Actors specified	Carrots	Sticks	Sermons	Not Specified
Actors specified	33.33% (3)	84.06% (58)	29.41% (5)	0.00% (0)
No actors specified	66.67% (6)	15.94% (11)	70.59% (12)	100.00% (2)
Total	100.00% (9)	100.00% (69)	100.00% (17)	100.00% (2)

Notes: This table shows the percentage (and number) of policy instruments that explicitly reference value chain actors for different instrument types. Column one, line one can be read as follows: Out of all Carrot type instruments, 33.3% (3) instruments explicitly reference a value chain actor - the remaining 66.67% (6) instruments do not explicitly mention an actor.

Table C.2: Instruments with actor specification and purpose

Actors specified	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Supply-Push	Demand-Pull	Other
Actors specified	76.81% (53)	52.94% (9)	44.44% (4)	0.00% (0)
No actors specified	23.19% (16)	47.06% (8)	55.56% (5)	100.00% (2)
Total	100.00% (69)	100.00% (17)	100.00% (9)	100.00% (2)

Notes: This table shows the percentage (and number) of policy instruments that explicitly reference value chain actors for different instrument purposes. Column one, line one can be read as follows: Out of all Life-cycle safety & traceability instruments, 76.81% (53) explicitly reference a value chain actor - the remaining 23.19% (16) instruments do not explicitly mention an actor.

Table C.3: Summary of Policy Mix Evaluation

Characteristic	Description	Dimension	Exemplary quote
Consistency	Lowering substance thresholds can reduce recycling rate in short to medium run	Inconsistency: instrument vs strategy	<p>“[...]With the upcoming amendments on [...] [on]the use of recycled plastics containing limit values of brominated flame retardants: If this continues, we rather not bother to put any effort into having [potentially contaminated plastic fractions] separated. Because it's really a restriction on the reuse of plastics. So, there is a barrier [...].”</p> <p>(WEEE sorting facility)</p> <p>“The current discussion on PFAS is a good one. There is an endless amount of PFAS molecules, so it's impossible to give a guarantee that none of these molecules are in there because besides what you know is being put in, you might be dealing with unknown degradation products from aging as well as during your extrusion. You might create degradation products, which are also PFAS. And in case of a family restriction, you end up not knowing what you have to look for. So that's definitely a challenge.”</p> <p>(Plastics Recycler)</p>
Consistency	Increasing the number of restricted substances can reduce recycling rate in short- to medium-run	Inconsistency: instrument vs strategy	<p>“And this is where we have a bit of concern with recycled content, because [...] at the minutes, there is not a methodology that can be used to test the exact product. It relies on [...] a chain of custody, which is fine if you can put in place that structure, but it means that there is the possibility of free riding. There's a possibility for unscrupulous players [...] placing the product on the market with, not maybe the right information going to the consumer at the end of the day [...].”</p> <p>(EEE manufacturer)</p> <p>“We are talking about a world market or a European market, but there is no [harmonized] end of waste for plastics. [...] Some member states don't trust what is being done in other member states. So they refuse any export [...].”</p> <p>(Plastics Recycler)</p>
Comprehensiveness	Lack of harmonized and mandatory quality and calculation standards for recycled plastic content	Incomprehensiveness: missing instrument	<p>“I think, because [the DPP] is on such a detailed level, that it doesn't reflect what's happening in our recycling process because our input is a diversity of materials. So having all the specific data [...], let's say a calculator on component level, the amount of materials that it uses, it's basically useless [...]. We can't use it in this way.”</p> <p>(WEEE sorting facility)</p> <p>“There is a gap between what the consumer does with his end-of-life product and the responsibility that the producer has to collect and properly treat it.”</p> <p>(Plastics recycler)</p>
Coordination	Information instruments (SCIP and DPP) are not well aligned with needs and workflow of sorting operators and recyclers	Lack of coordination: missing alignment of instruments	<p>“I think, because [the DPP] is on such a detailed level, that it doesn't reflect what's happening in our recycling process because our input is a diversity of materials. So having all the specific data [...], let's say a calculator on component level, the amount of materials that it uses, it's basically useless [...]. We can't use it in this way.”</p> <p>(WEEE sorting facility)</p> <p>“There is a gap between what the consumer does with his end-of-life product and the responsibility that the producer has to collect and properly treat it.”</p> <p>(Plastics recycler)</p>
Coordination	Insufficient amount of instruments are addressed at product users	Lack of coordination: actors are underaddressed	<p>“I think, because [the DPP] is on such a detailed level, that it doesn't reflect what's happening in our recycling process because our input is a diversity of materials. So having all the specific data [...], let's say a calculator on component level, the amount of materials that it uses, it's basically useless [...]. We can't use it in this way.”</p> <p>(WEEE sorting facility)</p> <p>“There is a gap between what the consumer does with his end-of-life product and the responsibility that the producer has to collect and properly treat it.”</p> <p>(Plastics recycler)</p>

Notes: This table summarizes the qualitative evaluation of how the policy mix for plastics circularity affects plastics recycling in the EEE sector. The evaluation is structured along the three policy mix characteristics, consistency, comprehensiveness, and coordination, and provides an exemplary quote from the interview data for each main finding of the analysis.

Table C.4: List of coded policy instruments

Instrument	Type	Purpose	Actor referenced	Policy	Year
Landfill Ban/Restriction	Sticks	Supply-Push	Producer/Holder Waste, Treatment Operator Waste	Landfill Dir.	1999
Landfill Site Operation Permit Requirement	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Treatment Operator Waste	Landfill Dir.	1999
Process Control and Monitoring Procedures During Landfill Operation	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Treatment Operator Waste	Landfill Dir.	1999
Requirements for the Closure of a Landfill Site and After-Care Procedures	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Treatment Operator Waste	Landfill Dir.	1999
Pricing Framework to Cover Landfill life-cycle Costs	Carrots	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Treatment Operator Waste	Landfill Dir.	1999
Economic Incentives for Waste Hierarchy Implementation	Carrots	Supply-Push	NA	Landfill Dir.	2020
Registration Requirements for Substances (on their Own, In Mixtures, In Articles)	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Importer Substance, Manufacturer Substance, Downstream User Substance, Distributor Substance, Producer Article, Importer Article, Distributor Article	REACH Reg.	2007
Requirements for Chemical Safety Assessment and Risk Control	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Importer Substance, Manufacturer Substance, Downstream User Substance, Producer Article, Importer Article	REACH Reg.	2007
Hazard Information Exchange Requirements	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Importer Substance, Manufacturer Substance, Downstream User Substance, Distributor Substance, Producer Article, Importer Article	REACH Reg.	2007
Prescriptions Regarding the Evaluation of Registrations	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Importer Substance, Manufacturer Substance, Downstream User Substance	REACH Reg.	2007
Restrictions & Bans of Hazardous Substances	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Importer Substance, Manufacturer Substance, Downstream User Substance	REACH Reg.	2007
Procedure for the Authorization Registered Substances	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Importer Substance, Manufacturer Substance, Downstream User Substance	REACH Reg.	2007
National Helpdesks for Guidance and Support	Sermons	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	NA	REACH Reg.	2007
Public Access to Chemical Substance Information Database	Sermons	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	NA	REACH Reg.	2007
Pre-Registration Requirements for Phase-In Substances	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Importer Substance, Manufacturer Substance	REACH Reg.	2007
Registration Requirements for Intermediates	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	NA	REACH Reg.	2007
Economic Incentives for Waste Hierarchy Implementation	Carrots	Supply-Push	NA	Waste Framework Dir.	2008
Classification Rules of Waste (End-of-Waste, Byproducts, Hazardous Waste)	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	NA	Waste Framework Dir.	2008
General Requirements on Waste Recovery By Type of Waste (Separately Collected & Hazardous Waste)	Sticks	Supply-Push	NA	Waste Framework Dir.	2008
Environmental and Health Safeguards for Waste Disposal and Recovery	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	NA	Waste Framework Dir.	2008

Table C.4: List of coded policy instruments (*continued*)

Instrument	Type	Purpose	Actor referenced	Policy	Year
Polluter Pays Principle & Prescriptions on the Responsibility for Waste Management	Sticks	Supply-Push	Manufacturer Product, Distributor Product, Producer/Holder Waste, Collection Operator Waste	Waste Framework Dir.	2008
Process Prescriptions for the Management of Hazardous Waste	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	NA	Waste Framework Dir.	2008
Digital Tracking and Reporting System for Hazardous Waste Operations	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Producer/Holder Waste, Treatment Operator Waste, Collection Operator Waste	Waste Framework Dir.	2008
Waste Management Operation Permits and Registration System	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Treatment Operator Waste	Waste Framework Dir.	2008
Ban of Abandonment, Dumping, and Uncontrolled Management of Waste	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	NA	Waste Framework Dir.	2008
Optional National Incentives for Eco-Friendly Product Design	Sermons	Demand-Pull	NA	Waste Framework Dir.	2018
Extended Producer Responsibility Requirements	Sticks	Supply-Push	Manufacturer Product, Distributor Product, Producer/Holder Waste, Treatment Operator Waste, Collection Operator Waste	Waste Framework Dir.	2018
Database Service for Chemical Substance Information	Sermons	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	User Product, Treatment Operator Waste	Waste Framework Dir.	2018
National Waste Prevention Strategies and Implementation Programs	Not Specified	Other	NA	Waste Framework Dir.	2018
Provision of Separate Waste Collection Systems	Carrots	Supply-Push	NA	Waste Framework Dir.	2018
Access and Support Measures for Waste Reuse Networks	Sermons	Supply-Push	NA	Waste Framework Dir.	2018
Provision of Separate Collection System for Household Hazardous Waste	Carrots	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	NA	Waste Framework Dir.	2018
Classification Requirements of Substances and Mixtures	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Importer Substance, Manufacturer Substance, Downstream User Substance	CLP Reg.	2009
Labeling Requirements of Hazardous Substances and Mixtures	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Importer Substance, Manufacturer Substance, Downstream User Substance, Distributor Substance	CLP Reg.	2009
Packaging Requirements of Hazardous Substances and Mixtures	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Importer Substance, Manufacturer Substance, Downstream User Substance, Distributor Substance	CLP Reg.	2009
Framework for Establishing and Maintaining Harmonized Classification of Substances	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Importer Substance, Manufacturer Substance, Downstream User Substance	CLP Reg.	2009
Framework for Managing the Classification and Labelling Inventory	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Importer Substance, Manufacturer Substance	CLP Reg.	2009
National Helpdesk for Chemical Classification Support	Sermons	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Importer Substance, Manufacturer Substance, Downstream User Substance, Distributor Substance	CLP Reg.	2009
Advertising Requirements for Hazardous Chemical Product Marketing	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	NA	CLP Reg.	2009
Restrictions of Hazardous Substances In EEE Products	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product, Distributor Product	RoHS Dir.	2011

Table C.4: List of coded policy instruments (*continued*)

Instrument	Type	Purpose	Actor referenced	Policy	Year
Requirements for Assessing Product Conformity and Documentation	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product, Distributor Product	RoHS Dir.	2011
Product and Operator Information & Traceability Requirements	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product, Distributor Product	RoHS Dir.	2011
Requirements for Corrective Actions on Non-Compliant Equipment	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product, Distributor Product	RoHS Dir.	2011
Requirements and Collaboration for WEEE Treatment and Reuse	Sermons	Demand-Pull	Manufacturer Product, Treatment Operator Waste	WEEE Dir.	2012
Provision and Requirements of Separate Collection Systems for EEE	Carrots	Supply-Push	Manufacturer Product, Distributor Product	WEEE Dir.	2012
Ban of Disposal of Separately Collected WEEE	Sticks	Supply-Push	NA	WEEE Dir.	2012
Requirement for the Treatment and Storage of Separately Collected WEEE	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Manufacturer Product, Treatment Operator Waste, Collection Operator Waste	WEEE Dir.	2012
Permit Requirements for Treatment Operations	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Treatment Operator Waste	WEEE Dir.	2012
Technology Development Support for Waste Management	Sermons	Supply-Push	NA	WEEE Dir.	2012
WEEE Recovery Target and Record Keeping Requirement	Sticks	Supply-Push	Manufacturer Product	WEEE Dir.	2012
Producer Responsibility Principle & Financing Requirement for WEEE Management	Sticks	Supply-Push	Manufacturer Product	WEEE Dir.	2012
Consumer Information and Cost Transparency Requirements for WEEE Management	Sermons	Supply-Push	Manufacturer Product, Distributor Product, User Product	WEEE Dir.	2012
Product Information Requirements WEEE Management	Sticks	Supply-Push	Manufacturer Product	WEEE Dir.	2012
EEE Producer Registration System Requirements	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Manufacturer Product	WEEE Dir.	2012
Shipment Documentation and Testing Protocol Requirements for Distinguishing EEE From WEEE	Sticks	Supply-Push	Producer/Holder Waste	WEEE Dir.	2012
Economic Incentives for Waste Hierarchy Implementation	Carrots	Supply-Push	NA	WEEE Dir.	2018
Product Safety Compliance Requirements	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product, Distributor Product	Low Voltage Dir.	2016
Requirements for Assessing Product Conformity and Documentation	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product, Distributor Product	Low Voltage Dir.	2016
Requirements for Corrective Actions on Non-Compliant Products	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product, Distributor Product	Low Voltage Dir.	2016
Product and Operator Information & Traceability Requirements	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product, Distributor Product	Low Voltage Dir.	2016

Table C.4: List of coded policy instruments (*continued*)

Instrument	Type	Purpose	Actor referenced	Policy	Year
Restriction & Ban of Production and Use of Pops on their Own, in Mixtures, and in Articles	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Importer Substance, Manufacturer Substance, Downstream User Substance, Manufacturer Product	POP Reg.	2019
National Emission Inventory Requirements for Regulated Substances	Sermons	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	NA	POP Reg.	2019
Public Procurement Requirements for Constructing New Pop Emitting Facilities	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	NA	POP Reg.	2019
Prescriptions on Handling Stockpiles Containing Pops	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Producer/Holder Waste	POP Reg.	2019
Prescriptions on Handling Waste Containing Pops	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Producer/Holder Waste, Treatment Operator Waste	POP Reg.	2019
Traceability Requirements of Waste Containing Pops	Sermons	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	NA	POP Reg.	2019
Pop Awareness and Training Programs	Sermons	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	NA	POP Reg.	2019
Technical and Financial Assistance Requirements for Supporting Convention Implementation in Developing Countries	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	NA	POP Reg.	2019
Ban of Pop Recovery Operations	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Treatment Operator Waste	POP Reg.	2019
Export Restriction of Waste - Prior Written Notification and Consent Requirements	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Producer/Holder Waste, Treatment Operator Waste, Collection Operator Waste, Dealer/Broker Waste, Disposal Operator Waste	Waste Shipment Reg.	2024
Export Restriction of Waste - General Information Requirements	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Producer/Holder Waste, Treatment Operator Waste, Collection Operator Waste, Dealer/Broker Waste, Disposal Operator Waste	Waste Shipment Reg.	2024
Waste Export Ban Framework	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Producer/Holder Waste, Treatment Operator Waste, Collection Operator Waste, Dealer/Broker Waste, Disposal Operator Waste	Waste Shipment Reg.	2024
Export Restriction of Waste - Audit Requirements of Facility in Destination Country	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Producer/Holder Waste, Treatment Operator Waste, Collection Operator Waste, Dealer/Broker Waste	Waste Shipment Reg.	2024
Waste Import Ban Framework	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Producer/Holder Waste, Treatment Operator Waste, Collection Operator Waste, Dealer/Broker Waste, Disposal Operator Waste	Waste Shipment Reg.	2024
Import Restrictions of Waste - Prior Written Notification and Consent Requirements	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Producer/Holder Waste, Treatment Operator Waste, Collection Operator Waste, Dealer/Broker Waste, Disposal Operator Waste	Waste Shipment Reg.	2024
Ban of Mixing Waste During Shipment	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	NA	Waste Shipment Reg.	2024
Requirements and Procedure for Failed Waste Shipment	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Producer/Holder Waste, Treatment Operator Waste, Collection Operator Waste, Dealer/Broker Waste, Disposal Operator Waste	Waste Shipment Reg.	2024

Table C.4: List of coded policy instruments (*continued*)

Instrument	Type	Purpose	Actor referenced	Policy	Year
Requirements and Procedure for Illegal Waste Shipment	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Producer/Holder Waste, Treatment Operator Waste, Collection Operator Waste, Dealer/Broker Waste, Disposal Operator Waste	Waste Shipment Reg.	2024
Electronic Information Exchange System for Waste Shipment Documentation	Sermons	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	NA	Waste Shipment Reg.	2024
Optional Fee Requirements for Waste Shipment Control Activities	Carrots	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Producer/Holder Waste, Collection Operator Waste, Dealer/Broker Waste	Waste Shipment Reg.	2024
Environmental Sound Management Compliance and Verification Requirements	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Producer/Holder Waste, Treatment Operator Waste, Collection Operator Waste, Dealer/Broker Waste, Disposal Operator Waste	Waste Shipment Reg.	2024
Digital Tool Implementation Requirements for Product Performance Verification (Optional)	Sermons	Demand-Pull	NA	Ecodesign Reg.	2024
Incentive Framework Requirements for High-Performing Products	Carrots	Demand-Pull	NA	Ecodesign Reg.	2024
Public Procurement Requirements (Optional)	Not Specified	Demand-Pull	NA	Ecodesign Reg.	2024
Information Requirements on Energy Use Data (Optional)	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product	Ecodesign Reg.	2024
Supply Chain Information and Traceability Requirements for Ecodesign Compliance	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product, Distributor Product, Dealer/Broker Product, Fulfilment Service Provider Product, Online Marketplace Product	Ecodesign Reg.	2024
Product Performance and Information Requirements Framework	Sticks	Demand-Pull	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product, Distributor Product, User Product, Treatment Operator Waste	Ecodesign Reg.	2024
Digital Product Passport Implementation and Management Requirements	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product, Distributor Product, Dealer/Broker Product, Fulfilment Service Provider Product	Ecodesign Reg.	2024
Product Passport Registry Requirements for Market Surveillance and Authentication	Sermons	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product, Distributor Product, Dealer/Broker Product, Fulfilment Service Provider Product	Ecodesign Reg.	2024
Product Labeling Requirements	Sticks	Demand-Pull	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product, Distributor Product, Dealer/Broker Product	Ecodesign Reg.	2024
Optional Industry Self-Regulation Framework	Sermons	Other	NA	Ecodesign Reg.	2024
Provision of Sme Training and Assistance	Sermons	Demand-Pull	NA	Ecodesign Reg.	2024
Transparency Requirements on Destruction of Unsold Consumer Goods	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product, Distributor Product, Dealer/Broker Product, Fulfilment Service Provider Product	Ecodesign Reg.	2024
Requirements for Assessing Product Conformity and Documentation	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product, Distributor Product	Ecodesign Reg.	2024

Table C.4: List of coded policy instruments (*continued*)

Instrument	Type	Purpose	Actor referenced	Policy	Year
Requirements for Corrective Actions on Non-Compliant Products	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product, Distributor Product	Ecodesign Reg.	2024
Product Sustainability Information Provision Requirements	Sticks	Life-cycle Safety & Traceability	User Product, Dealer/Broker Product, Online Marketplace Product	Ecodesign Reg.	2024
Anti-Circumvention Requirements for Product Performance and Updates	Sticks	Demand-Pull	Manufacturer Product, Importer Product, Distributor Product, Dealer/Broker Product	Ecodesign Reg.	2024

Notes: This table shows the full list of the 97 coded policy instruments included in the 10 legal policy documents. The table contains the summary of the content of each instrument (instrument column), the type and purpose, as classified by the researchers, the policy it belongs to, and the year the policy was adopted or published. In addition, it highlights the value chain actors that are directly referenced in the instrument. The actor names are used as they appear in the legal text. See table C.5 for how the names of the legal actors were grouped for the tables in the results part. NA indicates that no actor was addressed.

Notes: This figure illustrates a simplified life-cycle of plastics in electronic products. The different boxes refer to the life-cycle steps of plastics used in electronics. Dotted arrows highlight how recycling can contribute to transitioning towards a more circular economy.

Table C.5: Actor grouping

Actor	Legal definition	Legal document	Actor group
distributor substance	<i>'distributor' means any natural or legal person established within the Community, including a retailer, who only stores and places on the market a substance, on its own or in a mixture, for third parties;</i>	CLP, REACH	Substance Distributor
downstream user substance	<i>'downstream user' means any natural or legal person established within the Community, other than the manufacturer or the importer, who uses a substance, either on its own or in a mixture, in the course of his industrial or professional activities. A distributor or a consumer is not a downstream user. A re-importer exempted pursuant to Article 2(7)(c) of Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 shall be regarded as a downstream user; recipient of a substance or a mixture: means a downstream user or a distributor being supplied with a substance or a mixture;</i>	CLP, REACH	Substance User
recipient substance	<i>'recipient of a substance or a mixture: means a downstream user or a distributor being supplied with a substance or a mixture;</i>	REACH	Substance User; Substance Distributor
15 importer substance	<i>'importer' means any natural or legal person established within the Community who is responsible for import;</i>	CLP, REACH	Substance Importer
manufacturer substance	<i>'manufacturer' means any natural or legal person established within the Community who manufactures a substance within the Community;</i>	CLP, REACH	Substance Manufacturer
supplier substance	<i>'supplier' means any manufacturer, importer, downstream user or distributor placing on the market a substance, on its own or in a mixture, or a mixture;</i>	CLP, REACH	Substance Manufacturer; Substance Distributor; Substance User
producer waste	<i>'waste producer' means anyone whose activities produce waste (original waste producer) or anyone who carries out pre-processing, mixing or other operations resulting in a change in the nature or composition of this waste;</i>	WFD	Waste Producer and Holder
holder waste	<i>'waste holder' means the waste producer or the natural or legal person who is in possession of the waste;</i>	WFD	Waste Producer and Holder

notifier waste shipment	<p><i>'notifier' means:</i></p> <p><i>(a) in the case of a shipment originating from a Member State, any natural or legal person under the national jurisdiction of that Member State who plans or carries out a shipment of waste and to whom the duty to notify is assigned, and who is listed below:</i></p> <p><i>(i) the original waste producer;</i></p> <p><i>(ii) the new waste producer who carries out operations prior to shipment,</i></p> <p><i>(iii) a collector who, from various small quantities of the same type of waste collected from a variety of sources, has assembled the shipment which is to start from a single notified location;</i></p> <p><i>(iv) a dealer or a broker acting on behalf of any of the categories specified in points (i), (ii) or (iii);</i></p> <p><i>(v) where all of the persons specified above, are unknown or insolvent, the waste holder;</i></p> <p><i>(b) in the case of import into, or transit through, the Union of waste that does not originate in a Member State, any of the following natural or legal persons under the national jurisdiction of the country of dispatch who plans or carries out a shipment of waste or intends to have, or who has had, a shipment of waste carried out:</i></p> <p><i>(i) the person designated by the law of the country of dispatch;</i></p> <p><i>(ii) in the absence of a person designated by the law of the country of dispatch, the waste holder at the time the export took place;</i></p>	WSR	Waste Producer and Holder; Waste Collection Operator
distributor article	see definition distributor substance	REACH RoHS, WEEE, Low Voltage, ESPR	Product Distributor
distributor product	<i>'distributor' means any natural or legal person in the supply chain, other than the manufacturer or the importer, who makes an EEE available on the market;</i>	REACH RoHS, WEEE, Low Voltage, ESPR	Product Distributor
dealer product	<i>'dealer' means a distributor or any other natural or legal person that offers products for sale, hire or hire purchase, or that displays products, to end users in the course of a commercial activity, including through distance selling; and includes any natural or legal person that puts a product into service in the course of a commercial activity;</i>	ESPR	Product Distributor
provider of an online marketplace	<i>'provider of an online marketplace' means a provider of an intermediary service using an online interface which allows customers to conclude distance contracts with economic operators for the sale of products covered by delegated acts adopted pursuant to Article 4;</i>	ESPR	Product Distributor

fulfilment service provider	<i>'fulfilment service provider' means any natural or legal person offering, in the course of commercial activity, at least two of the following services: warehousing, packaging, addressing and dispatching, without having ownership of the products involved, excluding postal services as defined in point 1 of Article 2 of Directive 97/67/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council (31), parcel delivery services as defined in point 2 of Article 2 of Regulation (EU) 2018/644 of the European Parliament and of the Council (32), and any other postal services or freight transport services;</i>	ESPR, Regulation (EU) 2019/1020	Product Distributor
importer article	see definition importer substance	REACH	Product Importer
importer product	<i>'importer' means any natural or legal person established within the Union, who places an EEE from a third country on the Union market;</i>	RoHS, Low Voltage, ESPR	Product Importer
producer of a product	<i>'producer' means any natural or legal person who, irrespective of the selling technique used, including distance communication within the meaning of Directive 97/7/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 1997 on the protection of consumers in respect of distance contracts (2): (i) is established in a Member State and manufactures EEE under his own name or trademark, or has EEE designed or manufactured and markets it under his name or trademark within the territory of that Member State; (ii) is established in a Member State and resells within the territory of that Member State, under his own name or trademark, equipment produced by other suppliers, a reseller not being regarded as the 'producer' if the brand of the producer appears on the equipment, as provided for in point (i); (iii) is established in a Member State and places on the market of that Member State, on a professional basis, EEE from a third country or from another Member State; or (iv) sells EEE by means of distance communication directly to private households or to users other than private households in a Member State, and is established in another Member State or in a third country. Whoever exclusively provides financing under or pursuant to any finance agreement shall not be deemed to be a 'producer' unless he also acts as a producer within the meaning of points (i) to (iv);</i>	WEEE	Product Manufacturer
manufacturer (EEE) product	<i>'manufacturer' means any natural or legal person who manufactures an EEE or who has an EEE designed or manufactured and markets it under his name or trademark;</i>	RoHS, Low Voltage	Product Manufacturer
manufacturer product	<i>'manufacturer' means any natural or legal person who manufactures a product or who has such a product designed or manufactured, and markets that product under its name or trademark or, in the absence of such person or an importer, any natural or legal person who places on the market or puts into service a product;</i>	ESPR	Product Manufacturer

producer article	<i>'producer of an article' means any natural or legal person who makes or assembles an article within the Community;</i>	CLP, REACH	Product Manufacturer
supplier of an article	<i>supplier of an article: means any producer or importer of an article, distributor or other actor in the supply chain placing an article on the market;</i>	REACH	Product Manufacturer; Product Distributor
economic operator	<i>'economic operators' means the manufacturer, the authorised representative, the importer and the distributor;</i>	RoHS, Low Voltage, ESPR	Product Manufacturer; Product Importer
end user	<i>end user' means any natural or legal person residing or established in the Union, to whom a product has been made available either as a consumer outside of any trade, business, craft or profession or as a professional end user in the course of its industrial or professional activities;</i>	ESRP, Regulation (EU) 2019/1020	Product User
recipient of an article	<i>recipient of an article: means an industrial or professional user, or a distributor, being supplied with an article but does not include consumers;</i>	REACH	Product User; Product distributor
dealer waste	<i>'dealer' means any undertaking which acts in the role of principal to purchase and subsequently sell waste, including such dealers who do not take physical possession of the waste;</i>	WFD	Waste Collection Operator
collector waste	<i>'collector' means any natural or legal person carrying out waste collection as defined in Article 3, point (10), of Directive 2008/98/EC.</i>	WSR	Waste Collection Operator
collection operator	<i>any establishment or undertaking carrying out collection operations; the establishments or undertakings which collect or transport waste on a professional basis</i>	WEEE; WFD	Waste Collection Operator
broker waste	<i>'broker' means any undertaking arranging the recovery or disposal of waste on behalf of others, including such brokers who do not take physical possession of the waste;</i>	WFD	Waste Treatment and Disposal Operator
consignee shipment	<i>'consignee' means the person or undertaking under the national jurisdiction of the country of destination to whom or to which the waste is shipped for recovery or disposal;</i>	WSR	Waste Treatment and Disposal Operator
operator landfill	<i>'operator' means the natural or legal person responsible for a landfill in accordance with the internal legislation of the Member State where the landfill is located; this person may change from the preparation to the after-care phase;</i>	Landfill	Waste Treatment and Disposal Operator
treatment operator	<i>any establishment or undertaking carrying out treatment operations</i>	WEEE, WFD	Waste Treatment and Disposal Operator
treatment or disposal operator	<i>the facility where the waste is recovered or disposed of A legal or natural person owning or exercising control over a recovery facility facility which receives the waste</i>	WSR	Waste Treatment and Disposal Operator

Notes: This table illustrates the different legal actors and their definitions as stated in the policy documents. Where multiple legal documents are referenced, the same definition is used in these

documents. Column, *actor group*, shows the value chain group that each actor (as defined in the legal text) was assigned to in this paper.

References

Reichardt, K., Rogge, K., 2016. How the policy mix impacts innovation: Findings from company case studies on offshore wind in germany. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions* 18, 62–81. doi:[10.1016/j.eist.2015.08.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2015.08.001).